

ZULFIYAXONIM'S NAME IS ALIVE

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Annotation: This article focuses on the work and activities of Zulfiya Xanum.

The history of the world-famous creation and creation of his poems will also be discussed.

Key words: Poems, activities, spring has come to question you, life theme, Inxanum, Hamid Olimjon, Ghafor Ghulam, award.

Zulfiyaxanum is a woman of the Uzbek people. When we talk about her, we see the image of a brave and courageous mother. The meaning and significance of his poems touch everyone's heart. No matter how difficult his life may be, his actions show that he is always in search and aspiration. He has achieved a lot since his youth. For example, at the age of 23 she worked as an editor in a publishing house and at the age of 26 as a department head in magazines. It is not limited to admission to a pedagogical school. After graduating, he will continue his postgraduate studies at the Institute of Language and Literature. That's how he started his education and career.

His first poem was published in the newspaper "Ishqi" under the title "Sheets of Life". It is no coincidence that his poems are so popular and fascinating. Because Zulfiya looks at life differently than others, she can see all the bright aspects of life, she can see the beauty that people can't see, and she stands out in that aspect. Zulfiya's poems express feelings of purity, delicacy, and kindness. In particular, we can say that the days spent with Hamid Olimjon were the most beautiful and prosperous moments of his life. He is also a real mirror for the Uzbek people, a great person who has shown the charity of all Uzbek women.

One of the reasons for his great and boundless love for fiction was his family environment. The poet recalls his childhood: "My father

was called *dag İsmail Deyran*. My father was a hardworking blacksmith. I always enjoyed my father's profession as a fine companion. There was no one as powerful as my father. I was amazed to see the iron in my father's hands. His hands were able to shape a piece of iron into any shape and turn it into something human. I still dream of being like my father, but it is harder to get into a person's heart than to work with iron, and not everyone can catch fire like lightning... My mother used to say, "Smoke inside." He was always shy and dreamy, but I knew that his thoughts and thoughts were not dreamy, that he was naive and weak. The sadness in his soul, the sadness in his voice, were just qualities of his character.

I couldn't believe how many songs and legends, epics and stories my mother knew. These magical legends and fairy tales give us a lot of joy, captivate us, and each time give us a new charm. I am convinced that in my heart I was awakened by the words of my mother, an ordinary woman who is able to work miracles, who opens the world wide, who leads people to beauty.

Indeed, the contribution of his mother and father had a special impact on the young poet. The role of the real hero in his heart was created by his mother. Zulfiya was amazed that she could write articles without going out and talking to a lot of people, and sometimes it was unthinkable for her mother to know so many poems and stories.

After the death of Hamid Olimjon, difficult days began for him. There were times when I felt lonely. Hamid is in a very depressed mood during the days of losing Olimjon and cannot sleep at night. One of these days, the poem ends at night. The next day he went to the office and told Gafar Gulistan about the poem and said that he was very sad about life. He wants to go to a place where there are no human beings, no birds, no grass. Gafar then gives his advice to Zulfiya. He explains that life is still ahead, that humanity should not always stop searching and should always look up. Here are some tips from Gafar Gulistan, Zulfiya's colleague and confidant. He recites a poem he wrote at night. The title of the poem is "Spring has come to question you." Its text is as follows:

Spring has come in question, you
 In cool mornings, almost blossoms
 People tip, spring on the ground,
 The light of rain, the gentleness of the winds,
 Spring in velvet valleys, hills—
 How much did you love me, spring,
 You were fascinated by apricot blossoms.
 As if every cool wind had your life
 You captured it in your eyes and kissed it.
 How, my love, spring is coming again,
 He was looking for you, he was wandering around.
 He grabbed you by the collar and asked you,
 He was so young, and he withered.
 As he watches, you, in the forest,
 He went out looking for the garden you were walking

in
 The beauty of writing,
 He searched for the green above,
 When he could not find it, his patience ran out, and a
 storm came.
 He took his head to the cliffs,
 Looking for a tree in the mountains of Finland,
 He threw the rock of the mountains into the streams.
 One of the first shepherds to go to the mountains
 Where is the goat, said the interrogator.

Silence in the bar, frustration,
 I'm tired, I can't stand it—
 Then he politely went to bed,
 Balkan and Chinese kissed each other on the face,
 Transformed on my electric
 Slowly he informed me of himself,
 But I can't find you in my bed,
 As one point he started long,
 It was windy again, and it wandered,
 He asked me, breaking my heart:
 "Oh, when I arrived, I was greeted with laughter.

A song flowed and a river flowed
 "Asking me about if I'm lucky."
 Whipped me in glory?
 Why apricot blossoms do not bloom,
 Curly hair waving in the hand?
 Why the joy I brought
 Doesn't he come out and write?
 When a lovely morning,

Kindness is the only way to win,
 To be happy and to enjoy every day.

I always saw my beauty,
 Where is the singer, that dreamy guy?
 Why are there tears in your eyes, left?
 Why a black dress, white in your hair,
 Why are you so nervous in this spring?
 How can I answer little tongue,
 Did you catch the bus, I came with you.
 He also walked with grief,
 I can't look at the toothpaste.
 He searched for the tree in agony,
 The bird woke up and disappeared easily.
 Unstable with your memory,
 The flowers were budding,
 The secret of our bond
 A soft song that covered the street
 How close this song is,
 How vital, full of life,
 Covered in spring, in the hand you love
 Your voice sounded lovely, elegant.
 You are not dead, my love, you are alive,
 I still can't breathe without you,
 Happiness in my heart, your words in my hand,
 Living life, the pain of return.
 You dream at night, I remember the day,
 As long as I live, so do you!

This is the history of the creation of this poem. It is one of the poems dedicated to the death of Hamid Olimjon.

In conclusion, it can be said that Zohbaxat is a great poet who has a special and great place in Uzbek poetry. Her life and work have been an example for all people. Her vitality, fidelity and devotion to love are an example for all our young and old women.

List of used literature:

1) <https://www.uznet.com/uz/2020/07/>

